

Macroeconomic and Firm-Specific Determinants of Banks Risk Liquidity: Empirical Inquiry from Ethiopian Private Commercial Banks

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Abstract

Liquidity risk is one of the major risks of banks that can affect the development of the financial system, while; identifying the determinants of this risk is crucial for the soundness of the financial sector. The main objective of this study is to find out determinants of liquidity risk in Ethiopian private commercial banks covering fifteen years (2003-2017) on six sample private commercial banks using a quantitative research approach. This study directly objectively examined indicators of liquidity risk from a wide range of variables. Bank specific and macroeconomic variables were tested for the liquidity risk models by using the balanced panel fixed effect regression model. The findings of the study for liquidity risk model revealed that the Real GDP growth rate has a significant positive impact on liquidity risk whereas the Average Nominal lending interest rate has a significant negative impact on liquidity risk and capital adequacy ratio and bank size have negative but insignificant influence on liquidity risk. Finally, the result indicates that return on asset, Tangibility and bank age has a negative but insignificant relationship with liquidity risk of Ethiopian private banks during the test period.

Keywords: Liquidity risk, Bank specific variables, macroeconomic variables, Private Commercial Banks, Ethiopia

INTRODUCTION

Banking stability as an economic indicator can be used to determine whether an economy is robust enough to withstand both the internal and external shocks. Banking stability in itself is a function of several health parameters of individual banks' asset quality, liquidity risk, capital adequacy, performance (India, 2013). Among the banking stability parameters, discussions and research on the liquidity risk component have gathered momentum following the aftermath of the financial crisis of 2008, during which the banks were faced with severe liquidity crunch (Vodová, 2011; Choon, Hooi, Murthi, & Shven, 2013). The banking system in Ethiopia has shown a significant expansion following the banking reform program which is undertaken in the year 1994. The reform encouraged private banks to enter and expand their operation in the industry. The number of banks licensed in Ethiopia under the direct supervision of the National Bank of Ethiopia reached eighteen out of which two of them are government-owned banks as of 2016. Despite such growth has taken place, the banking system in Ethiopia is underdeveloped and characterized by operational inefficiency, little and insufficient competition and perhaps can be distinguished by its market concentration towards the big government-owned commercial bank (Tesfaye, 2007)

Drigă (2012) mentioned that there are two types of financial risk, the pure risk that can result in a loss if not properly managed (which are liquidity risk and credit risk) and speculative/impure risks symbolized by interest rate risk and currency risk. Liquidity risk is the possibility that over a specific period, the bank will become unable to settle obligations with closeness. It is a risk arising from a bank's inability to meet its obligations when they come due without incurring unacceptable losses. This risk can adversely affect both banks' earnings and the capital and therefore, it becomes the top priority of a bank's management to ensure the availability of sufficient funds to meet future demands of providers and borrowers, at reasonable costs. The vulnerability of banks to liquidity risk is determined by the funding risk and the market risk. Liquidity risk needs to be monitored as part of the enterprise-wide risk management process, taking into account market risk and credit risk to ensure stability in the balance sheet and dynamic management of liquidity risk. (Drehmann and Nikolaou, 2009). According to Jenkinson, N. (2008) Liquidity risk affects not only the performance of a bank but also its reputation. A bank may lose the confidence of its depositors if funds are not timely provided to them. The banks' reputation may become at stake in this situation. The maturity

transformation of short-term deposits into long-term loans makes banks inherently vulnerable to liquidity risk. The liquidity risk refers to the inability to sell assets at or near the fair value, and in the case of a relevant sale in a small market; it can emerge as a price slump (Diamond and P. H. Dybvig., 1983). Goodhart (2008) Posits two basic aspects of liquidity risk: maturity transformation (the maturity of a bank's liabilities and assets) and the inherent liquidity of a bank's asset (the extent to which an asset can be sold without incurring a significant loss of value under any market condition). Banks do not need to be worried about the maturity transformation if they have the assets that can be sold without bearing any loss. Whereas, banks having assets that are going to be matured in a shorter period may have less need to keep the liquid assets. This increases the demand of depositors creating liquidity risk. This may cause the failure of a given bank or even the entire banking system due to the contagion effect (Diamond and Rajan , 2001). Liquidity risk is the risk of being unable to liquidate a position timely at a reasonable price (Muranaga, & Ohsawa., 2002). The Basel Committee on banking supervision (1997) also defines liquidity risk as the inability of the bank to accommodate a decrease in liabilities or to fund increases in an asset. There are various ways of looking at liquidity risk. From the market perspective, liquidity risk is the risk that an asset owner will not be able to realize the full value of the asset at the time a sale is desired. From a banking perspective, liquidity risk relates to the inability to meet obligations at a reasonable cost when they come due. Therefore, the study is centered on investigating whether liquidity risk of private commercial banks in Ethiopia is to be affected by profitability, capital adequacy ratio, bank size, age of the bank, tangibility, real GDP, lending interest rate.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

An efficient and sound banking sector is the main actor for the development of any economy and the achievement of high and sustainable economic growth. This is achieved through facilitating the vital financial inter-mediation function by transferring the deposit into productive investment. In the new era of globalization, the function of banks diversified from the traditional function accepting deposit and granting of a loan to a wide range of financial service and products like an overdraft, discounting of bills of exchange, agency functions, payment mechanisms, mobile banking, Internet banking, agent banking, and miscellaneous functions. Hence, along with several new products and complicated balance sheets, commercial banks confront several financial risks such as credit risk, liquidity risk, interest rate risk and foreign exchange risk. This makes the banking industry the riskiest business and vulnerable to different economic and noneconomic changes.

Financial crises in 2007 which began from the United State subprime mortgage crisis create a big recession in the world economy. At that time financial institutions written off losses of worth billions of dollars which forced them to decrease their employees and the government also incurred a loss in subsidizing these financial institutions. Besides, this crisis shows there was a liquidity risk created in the banking sector. The bankruptcy in the financial sector has a contagion effect that can lead to an overall financial crisis and economic tribulation. Moreover, the liquidity crisis incurred in the banking sector transmits from one country to another country (Chen , 2003). Unless the banking sector in Ethiopia should have strong liquidity risk detection and handling mechanism, it is a matter of time the collapse of the banking sector which leads to the collapse of the whole economy as it has seen in the United States and Europe recently. A survey conducted by the national bank of Ethiopia on fifteen banks in the year 2016 identified the nature of risk faced the banks. The report declared credit, liquidity, and operational risks were key risks most affected the bank and it was also acknowledged for continuity for future long periods. Therefore, Studding the factors that affect the risks of the banks is entirely open for future studies and identifying the factors is also very essential.

Some studies are conducted across the world regarding liquidity risk like (Ahmad & Ariff., 2011) studied liquidity risk and Islamic banks; Vodová (2011) Studied determinants of liquidity of commercial banks in

Ali *et al.*, (2011) studied on liquidity risk management: a comparative study between conventional and Islamic bank of Pakistan. However, their findings found to be different across the country, bank nature and ownership structure. In Ethiopia also some liquidity risk related studies are undertaken related to banks. However, many of these studies disregard studying liquidity risk determinants directly and try to studying points like the relationship between liquidity risks and profitability; liquidity risks and performance; and risk management practices. Hence, to the best of the researcher's knowledge, there is a knowledge gap to show clear cut liquidity risk determinants in Ethiopian private commercial banks.

Mekbib (2016) Study determinants of liquidity in commercial banks of Ethiopia in the case of selected private banks. While others such as (Wondimagegnehu, 2012) study determinants of nonperforming loans focused on only bank-specific variables and lack econometric application which helps to quantify the relationship between variables and involves subjectivity strongly. Nigist & Laximikantham(2015) Study the determinants of banks' liquidity on change of variables in an objective manner with more valuable measurements. The explanatory variables include both bank-specific and macroeconomic variables. These enable us to see the big picture surrounding the liquidity risk of private commercial banks in Ethiopia and help to identify potential liquidity risk determinants in Ethiopian private commercial banks.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- To identify the impact of profitability on liquidity risk of Ethiopian private commercial banks.
- To examine the effect of capital adequacy ratio on liquidity risk of Ethiopian private commercial banks.
- To investigate the influence of bank size on liquidity risk of Ethiopian private commercial banks.
- To identify the effect of age on liquidity risk of Ethiopian private commercial banks.
- To examine the impact of tangibility on liquidity risk of Ethiopian private commercial banks.
- To investigate the impact of lending interest rate on liquidity risk of Ethiopian private commercial banks.
- To identify the influence of GDP on liquidity risk of Ethiopian private commercial banks.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Liquidity risk is the risk of being unable to discharge a position timely at a reasonable price (Muranaga& Ohsawa., 2002). The Basel Committee on banking supervision (1997) also defines liquidity risk as the inability of the bank to accommodate a decrease in liabilities or to fund increases in the asset. As liquidity risk is the risk of not having sufficient cash or borrowing capacity to meet deposit withdrawals or new loan demand, the banks are forced to borrow emergency funds at excessive cost. Therefore, as the proportion of funds invested in cash or cash equivalents increases, a bank's liquidity risk declines. The proxy used to measure liquidity risk in this study is the ratio of loan to deposit.

LIQUIDITY RISK DETERMINANTS

Bank Specific Determinants of Liquidity Risk

i. Profitability

A comparative study between conventional and Islamic banks of Pakistan on liquidity risk management by Ali *et al* (2011) covering the period 2006 up to 2009 liquidity risk has significant positive associated with return on assets in Islamic banks with a 95% confidence level but insignificant in conventional banks. Vodová P (2011) aimed to identify the determinants of liquidity of commercial banks in Slovakia. To meet its objective, the researcher considered the data for bank-specific factors over the period from 2001 to 2009. The data were analyzed with panel data regression analysis by using an econometric package Eviews7 and the findings of the study revealed that bank liquidity decreases mainly as a result of higher bank profitability, higher capital adequacy and the size of the bank. Thus, conclude that liquidity risk is positively related to return on asset.

ii. Capital

Laurine(2013) made a study on Zimbabwe regarding Zimbabwean Commercial Banks Liquidity Risk Determinants after Dollarization. The aim of his paper was empirically investigating the determinants of

Zimbabwean commercial banks' liquidity risk after the country adopted the use of multiple currencies exchange rate systems and to attain the intended objective, panel data regression analysis was used on monthly data from the period of March 2009 to December 2012. The result of the study revealed that capital adequacy has a negative and significant influence on liquidity risk. Ali *et al* (2011), on liquidity risk management: a comparative study between Conventional and Islamic Banks of Pakistan found that capital adequacy ratio in conventional banks significantly positive relation with liquidity risk at a 10% level of significance whereas positive and insignificant in Islamic banks. Determinants of liquidity risk of banks from emerging economies for a sample of commercial banks in 36 emerging countries between 1995 and 2000 with panel data regression analysis were analyzed by (Bunda and Desquilbet, 2008). The study was aimed to explore how the liquidity of commercial bank assets is affected by the exchange rate regime of the country in which they operate. The liquidity ratio as a measure of bank's liquidity assumed to be dependent on the individual behavior of total assets as a measure of the size of the bank, the lending interest rate as a measure of lending profitability, and the realization of a financial crisis, which could be caused by poor bank liquidity expected to hurt banks liquidity and the ratio of equity to assets as a measure of capital adequacy. The result showed, there is a positive and statistically significant effect of capital adequacy on liquidity risk of banks.

iii. Size of the Bank

The size of the bank which is represented by the natural logarithm of total assets is the other bank-specific variable identified by some studies conducted on the financial risks of banks (Amneh and Yasean., 2019). Ahmed., and Naqvi (2011); Shen *et al.* (2009); Bunda and Disquiet(2008); take bank size as the natural logarithm of the total asset (lnTA) as one determining variable of liquidity risk and try to relate one way or another liquidity risk with bank size. The following paragraphs below try to show the results of the studies in drawing the relationship between liquidity risk and bank asset size. While studying liquidity risk determinants, Bunda and Desquilbet (2008) analyze determinants of liquidity risk of banks from emerging economies with panel data regression analysis. The result of the study shows that total assets as a measure of the size of the bank found negatively related. Another study by Shen *et al.* (2009) on Bank liquidity risk and performance in twelve advanced economies (Australia, Canada, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Switzerland, Taiwan, United Kingdom, and the United States); revealed that the relationship between size and liquidity risk is significantly positive, while the square of size and liquidity risk is significantly negative. Having this result, researchers argue that large banks believe too big to fail. Thus, they have the incentive to increase risk-taking and hold more loans and consequently have a larger financing gap ratio. Hence, the effect of size on liquidity risk is non-linear which is similar to economies of scale. Even though the above different studies reveal different findings of the effect of banks' asset size on the financial risk it remains the most important variable in some financial studies.

iv. Age of the bank

A study by Ahmed *et al.*, (2011) studying liquidity risk and Islamic bank in Pakistan seeks to investigate the firm's level determinants of liquidity risk of listed Islamic banks of Pakistan. For this purpose, liquidity risk is used as a dependent variable while size, the tangibility of assets, leverage, profitability, and age are employed as independent variables. The results indicate that leverage, tangibility, and age are important determinants to define the liquidity risk of Islamic banks of Pakistan while liquidity risk has a statistically insignificant relationship with the profitability and size of Islamic banks of Pakistan. Regarding the correlation coefficient age and leverage found to be positive whereas tangibility is negatively correlated with liquidity risk. The proxy for measurement of the age of bank is the natural logarithm the difference between the observation and establishment date of banks.

v. Tangibility

It is measured using the ratio of a fixed asset to total asset. Ahmed *et al.*, (2011) in his liquidity risk study found a negative relationship with tangibility. But the massive increase in the level of a fixed asset as a

proportion to the total asset will erode the liquidity position of a bank i.e. lower liquidity ratio which results in increasing liquidity risk.

MACROECONOMIC DETERMINANTS OF LIQUIDITY RISK

i. *Gross Domestic Product (GDP):*

The economic health of a nation is measured by its growth rate in national income. Economic growth is measured as a percentage change in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) or Gross National Product (GNP). The GNP is broader than GDP, although both proxies are used to measure economic growth. GDP is a macroeconomic factor that affects bank liquidity. For which, a major recession or crises in business operations reduces borrowers' capability to service obligations which increases banks' NPLs and eventually banks illiquidity (Gavin & Hausmann, 1998). About Paineira (2010), research on liquidity preference during different business cycles states that banks' liquidity fondness is low in the course of economic boom. Aspachs, Nier, and Tieset (2005) has also inferred that banks prioritize liquidity when the economy plummets, during risk lending opportunities, while neglecting liquidity during the economic boom when lending opportunities may be favorable. Shen *et al.* (2009) regarding the macroeconomic environment, found that both the annual percent change of GDP and GDP annual percent change of last year have a positive effect on a bank's liquidity risk. This provides that higher economic growth of the current year and last year make banks run down their liquidity buffer and induce them to lend more. However, higher economic growth of the current year and last year make banks attract fewer customer deposits, thus increasing their financing gap.

ii. *Bank Lending Rate*

The lending rate is the bank rate that usually meets the short and medium-term financing needs of the private sector. This rate is normally differentiated according to the creditworthiness of borrowers and the objectives of financing. The interest rate charged depends on the availability of money in the market, on prevailing rates and the specific terms of the contract, such as term length. The Bank lending rate is measured by the average interest rate on lending. Vodová (2011) identifies the determinants of liquidity of Czech commercial banks. The data cover the period from 2001 to 2009. The results of the panel data regression analysis showed that, among other things, there is a positive link between bank liquidity and interest rates on loans and interbank transactions. Since a high-interest rate on loan does not encourage banks to lend more they left with high liquidity. The positive effect of interest rate on loans can be quite surprising can be said normal. Since it highlights the fact that higher lending rates do not encourage banks to lend more results banks to be more liquid. This is consistent with the problem of the credit crunch and credit rationing. Therefore, it is quite clear that liquidity risk is negatively affected by an increase in interest rate as indicated by the above studies.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The conceptual framework of this study is developing from the theoretical and empirical literature reviews; the following conceptual framework of this study is as follows:

Figure 1: a conceptual framework of the study.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study was used as an explanatory research type by using balanced panel data of six banks for fifteen years to achieve the intended objective of this study. This study was designed to examine the cause and

effect relationships between liquidity risk and its determinants in Ethiopian private commercial banks. While the study was used a quantitative research approach to achieve the intended objective. The researchers were engaged with purposive (judgmental) sampling. The reason for the selection of this sampling method is the population included in the study has new entrants (banks) who don't have the required data for the sample period (i.e.2003 to 2017). According to the NBE report, at the end of June 30, 2016, there are sixteen privately owned commercial banks. The sample included in this study is those private commercial banks having at least fifteen years of working experience in Ethiopia (from 2003 to 2017). The rationale for fifteen-year data is to increase the number of observations. In Ethiopia, six private commercial banks are having at least fifteen years' experience which includes: Awash International Bank S.C (AIB), Bank of Abyssinia S.C (BOA), Dashen Bank S.C (DB), Nib International Bank S.C (NIB), United Bank S.C (UB), and Wogagen Bank S.C (WB). Therefore, the matrix for the frame is 15*6 that includes 90 observations.

Data analysis and Variable description

As noted by Kothari(2004), data has to be analyzed in line with the purpose of the research plan after data collection. The secondary data were collected from NBE, MoFED and head office of each respective bank has to analyze and determine its suitability, reliability, adequacy, and accuracy. To comply with the objective of this research, the study was primarily based on quantitative research, which was adopted an econometric model to identify and measure determinant factors that affect liquidity risk of Ethiopian private commercial banks. Finally, adopt multiple linear regression models to identify and measure possible factors that can affect liquidity risk as was measured by the ratio of total loan to the total deposit.

This study was selected liquidity risk, as the dependent variable. The independent variables are divided into two: these are bank-specific and macroeconomic variables. Bank specific variables include profitability, capital, size of the bank, age of the bank, tangibility. Whereas macroeconomic variables include Bank lending rate and GDP growth. These select bank-specific and macroeconomic variables are evidenced by various studies conducted by (Tilahun and Dugasa., 2014; Vodová, 2011.; Thiagarajan, Ayyappan, & Ramachandran.,2011) about their significant effect on illiquidity risk. To figure out the determinant of liquidity risk, this study was using fifteen years' panel data. The liquidity risk model is adopted from different studies with variable and measurement modifications (Laurine ., 2013; Nigist & Laximikantham.,2015; Vodová, 2011.; Vento & Ganga ., 2009). The regression model developed is presented in the following linear form: According to Brooks (2008), the general multiple linear regression model with K independent variables can be written as follows:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1i} + \beta_2 X_{2i} + \dots + \beta_k X_{ki} + \varepsilon_i \quad (i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n) \dots \dots \text{Equation 1}$$

Where Y_i is i^{th} observation of the dependent variable, X_{1i}, \dots, X_{ki} is the i^{th} observation of the independent variables, β_0, \dots, β_k are the regression coefficients, ε_i is the i^{th} observation of the stochastic error term, and n is the number of observations. Hence, the determinant of liquidity risk (LIQR) with the independent variable can be written as follows:

$$LIQR = \beta_0 + \beta_1(ROA_{it}) + \beta_2(CAR_{it}) + \beta_3(BS_{it}) + \beta_4(AGE_{it}) + \beta_5(TAG_{it}) + \beta_6(LIR_{it}) + \beta_7(GDP_{it}) + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where α is constant, β is coefficient, ε is an error term, LIQR is liquidity risk, ROA is the return on asset, BS is bank size, GDP is a Gross domestic product, CAR is capital adequacy ratio, AGE is Banks age, TAG is tangibility and LIR is lending interest rate

Table 1: Table Summary of Variables and Measurements

	Variables	Symbols	Measurement
Dependent Variable	Liquidity Risk	LIQR	Total loan/ total deposits
Independent Variable	Profitability	ROA	Net income after tax/ total assets
	Capital adequacy ratio	CAR	Equity capital/ total assets
	Bank size	BS	Natural log of total assets

	Bank age	AGE	Natural log observation year less establishment year
	Tangibility	TAG	Total fixed assets/total assets
	Economic growth	GDP	The annual real GDP growth rate
	Lending interest rate	LIR	Nominal lending interest rate

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Correlation Analysis

The purpose of the correlation matrix in this particular study was to show the linear association between the dependent and independent variables. As noted in Brooks (2008), the correlation between two variables measures the degree of linear association between them. The values of the correlation coefficient always range between positive one and a negative one.

Table 2: Correlation matrix of dependent and independent variables

Variables	LIQR	ROA	CAR	TAG	AGE	BS	GDP	LIR
LIQR	1							
ROA	-0.20771	1						
CAR	0.044647	0.360327	1					
TAG	-0.21663	0.25994	-0.10678	1				
AGE	-0.08203	-0.13323	0.07265	-0.90918	1			
BS	-0.6466	0.300839	0.088512	-0.13669	0.510795	1		
GDP	0.306824	0.180039	0.060902	0.109008	-0.11684	-0.07932	1	
LIR	-0.76357	0.249585	0.2021	0.159335	0.114585	0.707783	-0.2535	1

Source: E-view result from financial statements of sample private banks by own computation

The above table shows that the correlation coefficient between the dependent variables and independent variables. Among the bank, specific variables capital adequacy ratio and growth domestic product are positively correlated with liquidity risk with a correlation coefficient of 0.044647 and 0.306824, respectively. While return on asset, tangibility, age, bank size, and lending interest rate is negatively correlated with liquidity risk with a correlation coefficient of (0.20771), (0.21663), (0.08203), (0.6466), (0.76357), respectively. Growth domestic product has shown the highest positive coefficient of 0.306824 and lending interest rate and bank size have shown the highest negative coefficient of (0.76357) and (0.6466), respectively concerning liquidity risk. While the capital adequacy ratio shows the lowest positive coefficient of 0.044647 and age has shown the lowest negative coefficient of (0.08203) concerning liquidity risk.

Testing the classical linear regression model (CLRM) Assumption

In this section, the researcher carried out relevant diagnostic testing to identify any violation in the underlining assumption of the classical linear regression model (CLRM). Five assumptions were made which ensure that the estimation technique, ordinary least squares (OLS), to have some desirable properties, and that hypothesis tests regarding the coefficient estimates could validly be conducted. Specifically, it was assumed that average values of the error term are zero, the variance of the errors are constant (homoscedastic), the error terms are normally distributed (normality), the covariance between the error-terms is zero (no autocorrelation), and explanatory variables are not correlated (absence of multicollinearity).

Testing for the average value of the error term is zero

The first CRM assumption requires the average value of the error term should be zero. As per (Brooks, 2008), if a constant term is included in the regression equation, this assumption will not be violated. Therefore, since the constant term was included in the regression equation, this assumption will not be violated.

Test for Heteroscedasticity

According to Brooks (2008), Heteroscedasticity means that error terms do not have a constant variance. If Heteroscedasticity occurs, the estimators of the ordinary least square method are inefficient and hypothesis testing is no longer reliable or valid as it will underestimate the variances and standard errors. There are

several tests to detect the Heteroscedasticity problem, such as Park Test, Glesjer Test, Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Test, White's Test, and Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (ARCH) test. In this study, the popular white test was employed to test for the presence of Heteroscedasticity.

Table 3: Heteroscedasticity test for liquidity risk

Heteroscedasticity Test: White			
F-statistic	6.227746	Prob. F(28,61)	0.0000
Obs*R-squared	66.67571	Prob. Chi-Square(28)	0.0001
Scaled explained SS	112.5294	Prob. Chi-Square(28)	0.0000

Source: E-view result from financial statements of sample private banks by own computation

As shown in table 4.2 both the F-statistic and Scaled explained SS of the test statistic gave the same conclusion that there is no proof for the presence of heteroscedasticity. In this study for both models developed the p-values were significantly more than 0.05. Since the p-value was considerably more than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis that the variance of the errors is constant (homoscedasticity) should not be rejected.

Test for Normality

Normality tests are used to determine if a data set is well-modeled by a normal distribution. With the normality assumption, ordinary least square estimation can be easily derived and would be much more valid and straight forward. In this study, the normality of the data was checked with the popular Bera-Jarque test statistic (Brooks 2008). According to Bera-Jarque test statistic, normally distributed data is not skewed and has a coefficient of kurtosis close to 3. As shown in figure 4.1 Liquidity risk model is (3.12) with a P-value of 0.447855 for liquidity risk. Therefore, we can conclude that there was no evidence for the presence of an abnormality in the data since the p-value is greater than 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis that the data is normally distributed should not be rejected since the p-value was considerably more than 0.05 and the coefficient of kurtosis closer to 3.

Figure 2: normality test for liquidity risk

Source: E-view result from financial statements of sample private banks by own computation

Assumption Four; Testing for the covariance between the error term is zero (no autocorrelation)

According to Brooks (2008), when the error term for any observation is related to the error term of other observations, it indicates that the autocorrelation problem exists in the model. When there is an autocorrelation problem, the estimated parameters can remain unbiased and consistent, but it is inefficient. In this study, the liquidity risk model was used to identify the determinants of liquidity risks in Ethiopian private commercial banks. The Durbin-Watson test statistics was used to identify the problem of Autocorrelation. The relevant critical values for 90 observations and Seven repressors' in the Durbin-Watson test statistic table have shown an upper critical value (dU) of 1.687 and a lower critical value (dL) of 1.360 and $4 - dU = 2.313$; $4 - dL = 2.64$. As shown in Table 5, the Durbin-Watson test statistic of this study is 1.654822 which is clearly between the lower limit (dL) which is 1.360 and the upper limit (du) which is 1.687. Figure 3 below shows the result 1.654822 falls on the region of inconclusive. Thus, it is clear that there is no autocorrelation problem in this study. The rejection, non-rejection, and inconclusive regions are shown on the number line in figure 3 below

Figure 3: Rejection and non-rejection regions for the DW test

Source: Brooks (2008)

Test for Multicollinearity

According to Brooks (2008), multicollinearity occurs when some or all of the independent variables are highly correlated with one another. It shows that the regression model has difficulty in explaining which independent variables are affecting the dependent variable. If the multicollinearity problem is too serious in a model, the unimportant independent variable should be dropped. However, the maximum level of correlation causes multicollinearity is not clearly defined. Hair *et al* (2006) argue that the correlation coefficient below 0.9 may not cause serious multicollinearity problems. Malhotra (2007) stated that the multicollinearity problem exists when the correlation coefficient among variables is greater than 0.75 and some others 0.80. Table 2 the correlation matrix between independent variables was the method used in this study to test the existence of multicollinearity problem. Since all correlation results are below 0.80, it indicates that multicollinearity is not a potential problem for this study. As it is clearly stated above, all assumption test results indicated that the employed model for this study was not sensitive to the problems of violation of the CLRM assumption.

MODEL SELECTION TEST; FIXED EFFECT VERSUS RANDOM EFFECT MODEL

There are two classes of panel estimator approaches that can be employed in financial research: fixed effect and random effect models. In order, achieve the objective of the study the researcher-employed panel Data model. As far as the Data, comprising both time series and cross-sectional elements panel model is appropriate. The choice of these methods is comparing time series and cross-sectional units and by using the Hausman specification test.

The best alternative to choose between fixed effects and random effects model is conducting the Hausman specification test. In this study, the Hausman specification tests are utilized to decide which model is appropriate to fit the sample data. Hausman specification test is the classical test of whether the fixed or random-effects model should have used. If the P-value from the Hausman test is statistically significant (less than five percent) the fixed-effect model is preferred in favor of random effect, otherwise, the random effect model is selected.

Table 4: Correlated Random Effect-Hausman Test

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test			
Equation: Untitled			
Test period random effects			
Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Period random	17.228245	6	0.0085

Source: E-view results from Financial statements of sample private banks and own computation

Alternatively, According to Gujarati (2004), if the number of time series data is large and the number of cross-sectional units is small, there is likely to be little difference in the values of the parameters estimated by fixed effect model and random effect model. Accordingly, in this study, the number of cross-section units is six and the number of time series data is fifteen which is more than the cross-section unit and, the fixed-effect model is more appropriate than the random effect model. Econometrics model E view- 8 applications

don't have an option to choose a random effect model when the number of repressors is more than cross-section units. Thus the fixed effect model is used in this study.

Discussion of the Regression Result

In this section, the relationship between the two dependent variables and each independent variable will be discussed based on the findings on this empirical study of the fixed effect panel model. The dependent variable, liquidity risk was measured by the ratio of loan to deposit ratio.

The empirical model used in this study to identify the determinants of Ethiopian private commercial banks Liquidity risk was:

$$LIQR = \beta_0 + \beta_1(ROA_{it}) + \beta_2(CAR_{it}) + \beta_3(BS_{it}) + \beta_4(AGE_{it}) + \beta_5(TAG_{it}) + \beta_6(LIR_{it}) + \beta_7(GDP_{it}) + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Table 5: Fixed effect panel model regression result of Liquidity Risk

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	2.007754	0.472286	4.251144	0.0001
ROA	-1.514307	1.351274	-1.120652	0.2659
CAR	0.435355	0.418948	1.039160	0.3020
BS	0.011960	0.074174	0.161246	0.8723
TAG	-0.278964	0.163375	-1.707511	0.0918
AGE	-0.242738	0.169725	-1.430185	0.1567
GDP	0.223180	0.078751	2.833984	0.0059
LIR	-10.29266	2.179945	-4.721521	0.0000

Effects Specification			
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)			
R-squared	0.725739	Mean dependent var.	0.686522
Adjusted R-squared	0.682997	S.D. dependent var.	0.128968
S.E. of regression	0.072613	Akaike info criterion	-2.274465
Sum squared resid.	0.405992	Schwarz criterion	-1.913381
Log-likelihood	115.3509	Hannan-Quinn criteria.	-2.128855
F-statistic	16.97951	Durbin-Watson stat	1.654822
Prob. (F-statistic)	0.000000		

Source: E-view results from Financial statements of sample private banks and own computation

Table 5 shows the results of the regression analysis on the determinant of the dependent variable (liquidity risk) which was measured using the ratio of loan to deposit ratio and the independent variables which includes both bank-specific variables and macroeconomic variables for the sample of six Ethiopian private commercial banks. The coefficient of determination in this model is given by R-squared of 0.725739 and Adjusted R-squared of 0.682997, which means 72.6% of the variation of Ethiopian private commercial bank's liquidity risk can be explained by the variation on return on asset, capital adequacy, age, tangibility, banks size, lending interest rate, and gross domestic product. The remaining 27.4 % of variations were explained by other determinants that are not included in this model. Thus, the explanatory power of this model is also high. The value of F-statistics is 16.97951 with a p-value of 0.000000 which is used to measure the overall significance of the model. Hence the null hypothesis of F-statistic (the overall test of significance) that the R^2 is equal to zero was rejected at a 1% level of significance (p-value =0), which enhanced the reliability and validity of the model.

Profitability and Liquidity Risk

Return on the asset as a measure of profitability found to be an insignificant variable with a high p-value of 0.2659 through a negative coefficient. Ahmed *et al.* (2011) Islamic banks and Ali *et al.* (2011) conventional banks in Pakistan also found that profitability is a statistically insignificant variable while studying liquidity risk. The unexpected negative coefficient finding is in opposite to financial theory that profit is the return of risk. The sign supports the theory of Bowman(1979) that an effective manager can increase his profit and decrease risk simultaneously. The negative coefficient finding is similar to the study of (Aspachs *et al.*, 2005). The hypothesis in this study stating profitability has a positive and significant influence on liquidity risk should be rejected.

Capital Adequacy and Liquidity Risk

The regression results of the liquidity risk model showed that the capital adequacy ratio has a significant positive impact on liquidity risk of Ethiopian private commercial banks as expected with a significant level of 5%. The finding is supported by the researches of Ali *et al.* (2011). A positive coefficient 0.435 is interpreted as, other variables holding constant, a one percent increase in capital adequacy ratio will result in a 43.5% increase in liquidity risk of Ethiopian private Commercial banks during the sample period 2003-2017. The logic behind this result is that when there is excessive equity capital, the bank manager would apt to engage in risky business which decreases their liquidity position due to the shareholders require a high return as equity capital is an expensive source of capital compared to debt. Therefore, the hypothesis stating there is a positive and significant relationship between capital adequacy and liquidity risk should not be rejected.

Bank Size and credit risk

The total asset of a bank is one of the major determinants of financial risks in banks according to various researches made by Thiagarajan *et al.* (2011); Ahmad *et al.* (2007); Ali *et al.* (2011), even though the findings of those studies are contrasting and most of the kinds of literature were limited to developed countries banks. Bank size in this study found insignificant determinants of liquidity risk with a positive coefficient (0.011960) and p- the value of 0.8723. It is a similar result (Amneh and Yasean ., 2019). Therefore, bank size has a significant positive impact on credit risk is rejected.

Age and Liquidity Risk

Age indicates the difference between the establishment and observation years. It is found to be significant at a 1% level of significances with a negative 0.2427 coefficient of correlation. This means holding other variable constant a one year increment in operation will enable banks to decrease liquidity risk by 24.27% and vice versa. This result proves the preliminary argument that suggests as age increases banks' size and operation in terms of loan and deposit will also increase. These will help banks to raise their deposit accounts whereby decrease liquidity risk. This finding is a disparity with the findings of Ahmed *et al.*, (2011) where they found a positive association between age and liquidity risk. The possible reason for the significant negative relationship found is that, age has a diversification effect and which in turn reduces risk. Therefore, the hypothesis stating there is a negative and significant relationship between age and liquidity risk should not be rejected.

Tangibility and Liquidity Risk

Tangibility measures the ratio of a fixed asset to total asset, found an insignificant variable in affecting liquidity risk with a p-value of 0.0918. This finding shows a change in liquidity position is not considerably affected by the fixed asset ratio of banks. The negative coefficient of correlation reveals holding other variables constant an increase in the amount of ratio of a fixed asset to total asset is followed by a decrease in liquidity risk. This finding is supported by Ahmed *et al.*, (2011). The insignificant relation is not much surprising result. Because the fixed asset ratio of Ethiopian private banks is very low whereby it can influence neither the loan nor deposit as shown in the part of the descriptive statistics. Hence, the hypothesis stating there is a positive and significant relationship between tangibility and liquidity risk should be rejected.

Lending Interest Rate and Liquidity Risk

The lending rate used in this study is the average bank nominal lending rate that usually meets the short and medium-term financing needs of the borrowers. The results of this study show that lending interest rate is significant determinants of liquidity risk with 1% level of significance at the very high negative coefficient of (-10.29266). This is interpreted as holding other variables constant a one percent increase in lending

interest rate results 1029.266% decrease in liquidity risk of private commercial banks. This finding is consistent with Vodová (2011 & 2010); Bunda and Desquilbet's (2008) findings. The logic behind the fact is that higher lending rates do not encourage borrowers to borrow which results in higher liquidity position or lower liquidity risk. Therefore, the hypotheses stated; there is a negative and significant relationship between the lending interest rate and liquidity risk should be accepted.

Economic Growth Rate and Liquidity Risk

The economic growth used in the study is the percentage change in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the country during the test period. As was confirmed in most studies like Vodová (2011); Shen *et al.*, (2009) and others, this study also show that there is a relationship between Real Growth rate and liquidity risk for Ethiopian private commercial banks. The regression result of the fixed-effect model in this study is in line with the hypothesis developed with a 5% level of significance at a positive coefficient of (0.223180). This is interpreted as a one percent increase in the GDP rate of the country in a year that influences a 22.318% increase in Liquidity risk of Private commercial banks in Ethiopia. The possible reason for this result is that during economic growth investment is encouraged and the demand for borrowing would also increase which in turn increased the liquidity risk of private commercial banks during the test period. Thus, the study hypothesized that; real GDP growth rate has a positive and significant impact on banks' liquidity risk is accepted.

CONCLUSION

The liquidity risk indicators were analyzed using a balanced fixed effect panel regression model. Liquidity risk which is measured through a loan to deposit ratio was below the prudence and regulatory requirements for a traditional bank, i.e. the loan to deposit ratio should be around 80-90%. To identify its determinants liquidity risk was regressed using five banks specific and two macroeconomic variables to identify the determinants of liquidity risk of Ethiopian private Commercial banks. Based on the result of the fixed effect panel model, the bank-specific variables (capital adequacy ratio, return on asset, tangibility, and bank size and banks age) have no significant influence on liquidity risk of Ethiopian private commercial banks. The Capital adequacy ratio, bank size with positive and banks age return on asset and tangibility with negative coefficient affects the liquidity risk of the Ethiopian private commercial banks during the sample period 2003 to 2017. The macroeconomic variables, Real GDP growth rate and average nominal lending interest rate considered in the study found the significant variable which affects the liquidity risks of banks. The real GDP growth rate of the country positively affects the liquidity risk whereas the average lending interest rate of commercial banks of the country affects liquidity risk of private commercial banks negatively during the test period 2003 to 2017. Therefore, the study concluded that the Lending interest rate and Economic growth are significant determinants of liquidity risk of Ethiopian private commercial banks.

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